

the volumetric determination of Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) and Y(III) in the pH range 4.8 and 5. The aliquots containing Nd(III), Sm(III) Gd(III) and Y(III) when titrated against standard EDTA solution in the presence of copper-thiomalate, give a sharp end point from violet to blue. The concentration range for the accurate determination of these metals is 1 to 40 mgs of Nd, 40 to 100 mgs of Sm, 1 to 60 mgs of Gd and 4 to 30 mgs of Y. When the results were compared with the results obtained using the conventional² indicator, they were found to be satisfactory. The following ions like Br⁻, MnO₄⁻, ClO₄²⁻, Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻, CNS⁻, CN⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, MoO₄⁻, PO₄³⁻, C₂O₄²⁻ interfere seriously. Small traces of NO₂⁻ increase the sharpness of the end point. The relatively cheaper indicator and sharp end point are the special features of the proposed method.

Procedure :

To the aliquot of the solutions containing Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) or Y(III) (the range mentioned above) 1 ml of Cu(II) solution (0.1M) and 1ml of 1% aqueous solution of thiomalic acid were added. The pH of the mixture was adjusted between 4.8 and 5 with acetate buffer. The mixture was then titrated against standard EDTA solution till the colour changed from violet to blue. The amount of EDTA for 1 ml of Cu(II) being known, amount of metal was calculated.

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Chemical Investigation of *Coleus aromaticus* Benth. Part II

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β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside and 5, 4'-di-hydroxy, 6, 7-dimethoxy flavone (cirsimaritin) have been isolated from the leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* (family—Labiatae).

The isolation of a few components have been reported earlier by various workers¹⁻⁵ from this plant.

Experimental

The percolation of air-dried powdered leaves (7 kg.) was carried out with 75% ethanol and the alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure at 50°. The concentrate was successively fractionated with hexane, ethylacetate and n-butanol.

Hexane fraction : The compounds isolated from hexane soluble fraction have already been reported by us⁶.

Ethyl acetate fraction : The ethylacetate soluble residue (25 g.) was chromatographed over silicagel (500 g.) and eluted successively with benzene, benzene : ethylacetate (3 : 1), benzene : ethylacetate (1 : 1) and ethylacetate.

Benzene : ethylacetate (3:1) eluate gave a compound which crystallized from methanol as light yellow needles, m. p. 255-6°. (Found : C, 64.5; H, 4.9. C₁₇H₁₄O₆ requires C, 64.9; H, 4.45%). The IR spectra showed characteristic peaks at 3280 (O—H); 1660(C=O); 1600, 1570 (C—C) and 1245 (C—O) cm.⁻¹. The compound gave positive test for flavonoids (pink colour with magnesium and hydrochloric acid). λ_{max} 220, 276 (band II), 333 (band I), (MeOH); 221, 301, 361 (AlCl₃) 238, 276, 395 (NaOMe); 220, 276, 333 nm (NaOAc and NaOAc+ boric acid). The absence of bathochromic shift in band II in the presence of NaOAc indicated the absence of 7-hydroxyl group in the flavone molecule. Since no shift in any band occurred with boric acid buffer, this ruled out the possibility of ortho-di-hydroxyl grouping in the molecule. A bathochromic shift of 28 nm in band I and 25 nm in band II in the presence of AlCl₃ indicated the presence of—OH group either at C-5 or at C-3. A bathochromic shift of 62 nm in band I without a decrease in intensity in the presence of NaOMe showed the presence of free 4'-hydroxyl group in the molecule. Mass spectrum : (m/e) : 314 (M⁺), 299 (M—C I₃), 286 (M—CO), 271 (286—CH₃), 254 (271—OH), 196 (M—118), 168 (196—CO), 153 (168—CH₃).

The compound was acetylated by Ac₂O pyridine at room temperature. The product thus obtained was purified by preparative TLC and the pure acetyl derivative was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 160°-61°, IR (KBr), 1748 (C=O) cm.⁻¹. The marked shift in the stretching frequency of C=O group in the acetyl derivative in due to the absence of hydrogen bonding which existed in the original compound. NMR (CDCl₃) ; τ 7.6 δ , 7.54 (3 H each, s, OCOCH₃) ; 6.13, 6.0 (3H each, s, OCH₃) ; 3.5 (H, s, 3-H) 3.13 (1H, s, 8-H) ; 2.81 (2H, d, J=9Hz) ; 2.18 (2H, d, J=9Hz). The nmr signal at τ value 3.5 showed the presence of C-3 proton and, therefore, one hydroxyl group is present at C-5. Low field absorption by two protons (doublets) at τ 2.81 and two protons (doublets) at τ 2.18 indicated that the —OH group of ring B is present at C-4'. The positioning of —OH group at C-4' makes available two sets of doublets of 3'-H, 5'-H and 2'-H, 6'-H. The compound gave positive test with Gibb's reagent indicating the presence of unsubstituted CH para to a phenolic group. Thus two methoxy groups can be positioned at C-6 and C-7. On the basis of these physico-chemical evidence the compound was assigned to be 5, 4'-di-hydroxy, 6, 7-di-methoxy flavone⁷ (cirsimaritin).

Since the authentic sample of cirsimaritin was not available, the direct comparison by co TLC, m. m. p. determination and superimposable IR spectra could not be done.

Both benzene : ethylacetate (1:1) and ethylacetate eluate gave a white solid which crystallized from methanol into white crystals, m. p. 288°-90°, $[\alpha]_D^{22} -43.6^\circ$ (pyridine). The compound gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test (purple→green) for steroids. The compound responded positively to Feigl test by turning aniline acetate paper pink on heating with phosphoric acid. Acetate m. p. 169°-70° (Found : C, 69.13 ; H, 9.4. $C_{43}H_{88}O_{10}$ requires C, 69.35 ; H, 9.14%). NMR spectrum indicated it to be tetraacetate.

The hydrolysis of the compound with 6N HCl yielded a residue which crystallized from ethanol, m. p. 136°-7° and was identified to be β -sitosterol. The aqueous portion of the hydrolysate showed one spot for sugar on paper chromatography, identical with glucose. The compound was identified as β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside by comparing IR spectra, co TLC and m. m. p. determination with an authentic sample.

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